

Reproducibility of “A Light-Weight Strategy for Restraining Gender Biases in Neural Rankers”

Group 12-B

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This paper aims to address the critical issue of gender bias in neural retrieval systems based on the research article “A Light-Weight Strategy for Restraining Gender Biases in Neural Rankers”. Recent studies have shown that neural retrieval methods may unintentionally amplify gender biases. The paper introduces a novel, simple, yet effective sampling strategy for training neural rankers, aiming to mitigate gender biases while maintaining retrieval effectiveness. The strategy involves a systematic approach to document sampling based on the degree of gender bias, significantly reducing biases without compromising the performance of state-of-the-art neural rankers. The effectiveness of this method is demonstrated through extensive experiments using the MS MARCO collection and various query datasets specifically designed for bias evaluation.

CCS CONCEPTS • Information retrieval • Neural networks • Learning biases •

1 Introduction

The reproduced paper proposes a novel, lightweight strategy designed to restrain gender biases in neural rankers. The approach is distinct in its simplicity and efficiency, enabling the reduction of biases without necessitating extensive changes to the underlying model architecture. The paper presents a two-fold contribution: first, a detailed analysis of the nature and extent of gender biases in current neural ranking models and secondly, an empirically validated method that demonstrates the effectiveness of the researchers’ strategy in reducing these biases while maintaining high levels of retrieval performance.

2. Experimental setup

The experimental setup involves the use of the MS MARCO dataset, a large-scale collection used for training and evaluating text retrieval models. The authors apply their strategy to several neural rankers, including models like BERT and ELECTRA, which are known for their effectiveness in various natural language processing tasks. The key aspect of the experiment is the implementation of a negative sampling strategy, which selectively includes biased samples in the training process. It is expected that by using this strategy, the model will be able to learn to minimize gender biases while still doing well in retrieval. Through analysis and replication, this study seeks to determine the validity of the published results based on our experimental data, the statistical significance of the findings, and the amount of information supplied in the paper sufficient to reproduce the results.

2.1 Proposed Approach

The proposed approach in "A Light-Weight Strategy for Restraining Gender Biases in Neural Rankers" introduces a unique negative sampling strategy for training neural rankers. This strategy involves selectively incorporating gender-biased negative samples during training. The aim is to make the rankers less prone to gender bias while maintaining their overall performance in retrieving relevant information. The approach focuses on modulating the degree of biased samples included in the training process through a parameter λ , enabling a balance between bias reduction and retrieval effectiveness. This method represents an innovative and practical solution to address gender bias in neural ranking models.

3 Reproducibility

In the experiment reproducibility phase, we aimed to replicate the methodology outlined in the paper. This involves setting up a similar experimental environment, including the use of the MS MARCO dataset and the same neural rankers.

By analyzing the code provided on the Github repository, the actions and instructions provided were sufficient to construct the project code files. In order to run the code, we encountered slight challenges by needing to update the packages and understand the overall flow of the steps. Firstly, running the reranking.py was time-consuming, as the training execution for one model took around 15 hours.

3.1 Reproduction Workflow

Preliminary setup

- Literature review and dataset acquisition (the link to the MSMARCO data was provided in the Github repository)

Reproduction of Models

- Set up baseline neural rankers
- Implement original negative sampling

Evaluation Metrics Setup

- Implement MRR@10 and bias metrics

Reproducing Experiments

- Train baseline models with the provided training set and strategies
- Validate against MS MARCO Dev Set
- Systematically change λ values
- Observe the impact on neural rankers

Analysis and refinement

- Analyze and compare reproduced results with reported paper results
- Conduct significance tests
- Measure differences between results

Reporting

- Create visual representations for clear insights

In theory, to train the neural ranking models with the proposed strategy, the first step was to download the fairness-aware training dataset, which includes biased and unbiased documents. A cross-encoder architecture is utilized from the Sentence Transformer Library for model training, incorporating the fairness-aware dataset. After training, we run the reranker.py to rerank documents for given queries. The primary issue encountered was the inability to directly utilize the output generated

by the reranking.py script (i.e., reranked documents) as input for the next stage, specifically for computing error metrics, as suggested by the GitHub repository. The evaluation of the model's performance is done using MRR_calculator.py. The following metrics for calculating bias (ARaB) and fairness (NFaiRR) were adapted from Navid Rekabsaz's work [2]. The estimations are calculated by processing the document neutrality scores and then computing fairness metrics for different thresholds. The FaiRRMetric utilizes a background document set to establish ideal fairness scores (IFaiRR) and compares these with actual retrieval results to calculate normalized fairness scores (NFaiRR).

3.2 Challenges

The authors provide details about their proposed sampling approach, along with a GitHub repository [link](#) and a reference to the documentation for the HuggingFace pre-trained models. The repository encompasses implementations for reranking documents, initially retrieved by rankers like BM25, pre-trained models, datasets used for training and evaluation, and metrics calculation.

Details on the model training and the proposed negative sampling strategy were not provided. However, the instructions from the paper and GitHub repository were sufficient for a re-implementation yielding somewhat similar results, based on the already trained models. While the paper mentions the models fine-tuned with their sampling strategy, it lacks information on the fine-tuning parameters (e.g., number of epochs, loss etc.) and provides no details about the parameters of the initial ranker BM25.

3.3 Result Analysis

3.3.1 Comparative Result

This comparative analysis focuses on key performance metrics such as model accuracy and bias measurements, enabling a clear understanding of the similarities and differences between the two sets of results.

3.3.2 Statistical Tests

The table presents a comparison between the performance of neural rankers trained with the original, ADVBERT, and the proposed strategy at a cut-off of 10. The metrics for evaluation include MRR@10, NFaiRR Value, NFaiRR Improvement, ARaB TF, ARaB TF Reduction, ARaB Boolean, and ARaB Boolean Reduction.

- The MRR@10 scores show that the proposed strategy generally results in a slight decrease in retrieval effectiveness compared to the original but is competitive with the ADVBERT strategy.
- The NFaiRR Value, which measures the fairness of the retrieval process, is higher for the proposed strategy across both BERT-Tiny and BERT-Mini models, indicating an improvement in fairness.
- The NFaiRR Improvement percentages are substantial, especially for BERT-Tiny, suggesting that the negative sampling strategy effectively enhances fairness in the ranking results.
- The ARaB TF and Boolean metrics, which measure bias based on the presence and frequency of gendered terms are reduced, indicating a decrease in bias.
- The ARaB Reduction percentages are quite notable in the approach for both TF and Boolean metrics, highlighting that it considerably reduces gender biases in the retrieved documents.

All in all, the result suggests that while there is a minor trade-off in retrieval performance (MRR@10), this approach significantly improves fairness (NFaiRR) and reduces bias (ARaB) in neural rankers, which is an important consideration in developing ethical AI systems.

Neural Ranker	Training Schema	MRR@10	NFaiRR Value	NFaiRR Improvement	ARaB TF	ARaB TF Reduction	ARaB Boolean	ARaB Boolean Reduction
BERT-Tiny	Original (Run)	0.1724	0.8650	-	0.0342	-	0.0284	-
BERT-Tiny	ADVBERT (Run)	0.1357	0.9263	7.08%	0.0228	33.33%	0.0219	22.89%
BERT-Tiny	Ours (Run)	0.1468	0.9731	12.49%	0.0097	71.64%	0.0103	63.73%
BERT-Mini	Original (Run)	0.2039	0.8756	-	0.0296	-	0.0248	-
BERT-Mini	ADVBERT (Run)	0.1492	0.9398	7.33%	0.0076	74.32%	0.0034	86.29%
BERT-Mini	Ours (Run)	0.1987	0.9634	10.02%	0.0139	53.04%	0.0117	52.82%

Table 1. Comparison of Results using the pre-trained models provided in the Github Repository

4. Conclusion

The absence of a training script and the proper documentation posed significant challenges for our team as we tried to apply the training process for the models. Without clear guidelines and parameters, we found ourselves struggling with the task of determining the most effective approach to training. This led to a point of uncertainty regarding the adequacy of the paper’s training procedures. As the training process extended over a considerable amount of time, together with the difficulty of training the models on our machines, concerns grew about the efficiency and effectiveness of our efforts. Nonetheless, we were able to replicate the results of the paper by using the provided trained models.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bigdeli, A., Arabzadeh, N., Seyedsalehi, S., Zihayat, M., & Bagheri, E. (2022). A Light-Weight Strategy for Restraining Gender Biases in Neural Rankers, (ECIR 2022)
- [2] Rekabsaz, N., Schedl, M.: Do neural ranking models intensify gender bias? In: Proceedings of the 43rd International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval, pp. 2065–2068 (2020)